

VALIDATION OF A MULTISTRATEGY ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR BATTERY IN PV PLANTS

Celena Lorenzo^a, Laura Barrutia^a, Luis Narvarte^a, Jesús Heras^b, Carlos Awadallah^b
^aInstituto de Energía Solar - Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28031 Madrid, Spain
^bWattkraft España, 28046, Madrid, Spain

c.lorenzon@upm.es

ABSTRACT: The integration of Li-ion batteries with photovoltaic (PV) plants is crucial for enhancing grid stability and maximizing renewable energy utilization. However, advanced Energy Management Systems (EMS) are required to optimize battery operation for both performance-oriented and regulation-oriented services. This paper presents the preliminary validation of a smart EMS for a grid-connected PV-battery system, tested at the UPM facilities. The EMS implements five control strategies: Time-of-Use arbitrage, Peak Shaving, Maximization of Self-Consumption, Frequency Regulation, and Capacity Market participation. Preliminary results demonstrate accurate power tracking (RMSE < 0.25 kW) and rapid response times (<650 ms) for the first three strategies, confirming the system's readiness for grid services. While current performance is suitable for capacity markets, faster response times are needed for ancillary services. Future work will integrate an AI-based market predictor to enable dynamic strategy selection and improve economic returns.

Keywords: Li-ion batteries, Energy Management System (EMS), photovoltaic systems, grid services

1 INTRODUCTION

The mitigation of climatic change and the depletion of fossil fuels are leading to a very fast energy transition, where electrification is playing a key role [1]. Electrification goes hand in hand with the large-scale deployment of renewable energy. However, the increasing penetration rates of intermittent energy sources (mainly wind and solar) are putting at risk the stability of the electric grids [2]. A recent example was the blackout that affected the interconnected electrical grid of Spain and Portugal on April 28, 2025, where the lack of sufficient operational energy reserves for frequency regulation was one of the key causes that led to the grid's collapse [3].

The integration of energy storage systems is one of the most powerful tools for strengthening the power grid. In particular, the use of Li-ion batteries integrated with PV systems is one of the solutions to this problem to receive more attention [4], [5], [6]. Although a lot has already been done [7][2], [8], [9], advanced Energy Management Systems (EMS) are necessary for better optimization of the system performance and of the energy trading of PV plants.

Furthermore, one of the main barriers to the massive deployment of Li-ion batteries is still their high cost [10]. Control strategies that improve the performance of the PV plant will increase its economic revenue. In addition, control strategies related to grid regulation (i.e. frequency regulation, contingency market, capacity market...) have a great economical potential, as the grid operators pay considerable amounts just for availability [11]. To amortize the initial investment cost of the battery in a reasonably short period of time, it is necessary to combine both types of strategies (performance-oriented and regulation-oriented).

This paper presents the preliminary results for the validation of a smart EMS system for the integration of batteries in PV plants. This validation is taking place with an outdoor demonstrator at the UPM facilities. The smart EMS will be able to integrate different control strategies, attending to different objectives. Some of these strategies are already commercially available (for example, the Maximization of Self-Consumption) and others are more

innovative (for example, Grid-Ancillary Services). There will be two operation modes: manual (where a certain control strategy is selected) and automatic (where the EMS itself will be able to decide which one of the control strategies is more convenient, depending on several external factors like the market prices for different services).

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Objectives and validation planning

This work is part of a European research project called PVOP [12], that aims at the innovative digitalization of the PV sector. One of the central lines of work is related to the control of PV plants to optimize their performance. The main objectives of this line of work are:

- To develop and demonstrate technical solutions for the control of PV plants to maximize their performance.
- To optimize the energy trading of PV plants with batteries.

For achieving these objectives, the smart EMS for a Li-ion battery will be implemented in two phases:

1. An alpha version is being currently developed, integrated and validated in an outdoor demonstrator at the UPM facilities. This demonstrator is composed of a Li-ion battery (model LUNA 97kWh/100kW), powered by a 16 kW_p PV generator and connected to the electric grid (although capable of stand-alone operation), according to Figure 1:

Figure 1: Schematic of the demonstrator at the UPM facilities.

- Using the lessons learnt during the alpha version validation, a beta version will be implemented and validated in a real PV power plant, under real operation conditions.

This paper presents the preliminary results for the validation of the alpha version, including some of the control strategies that will be implemented in the smart EMS.

2.2 Control strategies

There are five different control strategies that will be implemented in the smart EMS: three of them are performance-oriented (TOU, PS and MSC) and two, regulation-oriented (FR and CM). They are described in Table I:

Table I: Battery control strategies to be implemented in the smart EMS.

Operating modes	Revenue Generation	Return on Investment
Time of Use (TOU) Arbitrage	TOU arbitrage involves charging the battery during off-peak hours when electricity prices are low and discharging during peak hours when prices are high. This process allows the BESS to capitalize on price differentials by buying low and selling high	Consistently leveraging daily market fluctuations generates regular income, contributing to the overall revenue stack and shortening the payback period.
Peak Shaving (PS)	Peak shaving reduces the demand charges on electricity bills by lowering the peak demand during high-consumption periods. By discharging the battery during peak times, businesses can	A significant reduction in demand charges, which can constitute a large portion of industrial and commercial electricity bills, directly improves net income. This cost-saving

	avoid the highest tariff rates associated with their peak usage.	measure adds to the revenue stack, accelerating the return on investment. This operation mode can avoid Grid reconstruction (AGR).
Maximization of Self-Consumption (MSC)	This mode ensures that energy generated by a PV system is used as much as possible on-site rather than being exported to the grid at lower rates. The BESS stores excess solar energy during the day for use during the night or periods of low generation.	Maximizing self-consumption reduces dependency on grid electricity, leading to substantial savings on energy bills. These savings contribute to the revenue stack, resulting in a faster recovery of the BESS investment.
Frequency Regulation (FR) and Ancillary Services	Providing grid services such as frequency regulation, voltage support, and spinning reserve can generate additional income. Utilities and grid operators often pay for these ancillary services to maintain grid stability and reliability.	Participating in these markets provides a steady revenue stream, adding to the revenue stack and ensuring a quicker payback period.
Capacity Market (CM)	Capacity markets allow BESS owners to receive payments for being available to supply energy during high-demand periods, ensuring sufficient capacity for grid stability.	By participating in these markets, the BESS earns additional income simply by being available, which adds to the revenue stack and contributes to faster investment recovery.

The three performance-oriented strategies (TOU, PS and MSC) have already been validated for two different consumption profiles (during two complete days for each profile). These profiles were simulated in order to be representative of a typical residential and industrial consumptions. The real PV production of the PV generator

was scaled-up in order to be of a similar magnitude as the consumption.

The FR and CM strategies do not require of a specific control validation: it is only necessary to assure that the battery can deliver/absorb a certain amount of energy (with high accuracy) in a short period of time (as demanded by the grid operator). Both metrics (accuracy when following a power setpoint and response time) have been characterized during the validation of the three other strategies.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Time of Use (TOU)

The objective of this strategy is to set a charge and a discharge period for the next day, depending on the electricity prices announced by the grid operator. When the prices are lower, the battery will charge from the grid; when the prices are higher, it will sell the electricity to the grid. For the validation of this strategy, the PV energy was directly self-consumed by the university.

Figure 2 presents the power profiles (commands sent to the battery, loads consumption, PV inverters active power, charge and discharge battery power and energy at the Point of Injection -POI-) for a complete day with the TOU control implemented. It can be observed that the battery is charged between 13-15h (when electricity prices were lower) and discharged between 21-23h (when electricity prices were higher).

Figure 2: Power profiles during the validation of the TOU control strategy.

The KPIs obtained during the TOU validation are the following:

- $RMSE (P_{SetPoint,Battery} - P_{measured,Battery}) < 0.25 \text{ kW}$
- $t_{transition} < 600 \text{ ms}$
- $\frac{\text{Energy trade during TOU hours}}{\text{Total energy trade}} = 100\%$

3.2 Peak Shaving (PS)

The objective of this strategy is to use the battery to stop the system from going over the contracted power limit. This happens when consumption is too high and the available PV power isn't enough.

Figure 3 presents the power profiles (commands sent to the battery, loads consumption, PV inverters active power, charge and discharge battery power) for a complete day with the PS control implemented. It can be observed that the battery is charged with the PV surplus and discharged when the loads consumption exceeds the PS threshold. The result is that the POI measures exceed this threshold but very briefly. Actually, when calculating the total energy consumed for every 15-minutes period (which is the period that the grid operator considers for detecting

an excess in consumption), the grid limitation was always respected.

Figure 3: Power profiles during the validation of the PS control strategy.

The KPIs obtained during the PS validation are the following:

- $RMSE (P_{SetPoint,Battery} - P_{measured,Battery}) < 0.2 \text{ kW}$
- $t_{transition} < 500 \text{ ms}$
- $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} P_{imp/exp,G} \leq P_{max,G} \times 15 \text{ min} : 100\%$

3.3 Maximization of Self-Consumption (MSC)

The objective of this strategy is to use the battery for storing PV energy when it exceeds the loads consumption, and discharging when the consumption exceeds the PV production. This way, the PV self-consumption is maximized.

Figure 4 presents the power profiles (commands sent to the battery, loads consumption, PV inverters active power, charge and discharge battery power) for a complete day with the MSC control implemented. It can be observed that the battery is charged when the PV production is high (during the central hours of the day) and discharged when the PV production decreases in the morning and in the evening. This way, the excess of PV energy at midday is later used for covering the evening consumption. In consequence, less PV energy is sold to the grid, and less electricity is bought from it. This does not only represent an economic advantage, but also avoids the congestion of the transmission electric lines.

Figure 4: Power profiles during the validation of the MSC control strategy.

The KPIs obtained during the PS validation are the following:

- $RMSE (P_{SetPoint,Battery} - P_{measured,Battery}) < 0.25 \text{ kW}$
- $t_{transition} < 650 \text{ ms}$
- $Self - Consumption Rate = 82 - 100\%$

4 CONCLUSIONS

-The three control strategies -TOU, PS and MSC- have been correctly implemented. The different control logics have fulfilled their objectives: charging/discharging when indicated depending on the electricity market prices (TOU), avoiding that the energy at the Point of Injection exceeds a certain power limit (PS) and maximizing the PV self-consumption for reducing the PV surplus sold to the grid (MSC).

-The EMS fulfils the power commands with good accuracy: the mean RMSE is lower than 0.25kW, while the power commands range between 5-100kW.

-Response times are sufficient for normal FR and CM, where batteries need to be able to act in 2-3s [8].

-Response times might be insufficient for contingency markets, which are part of Ancillary Services, where batteries need to be able to act in 200-300ms [13].

The next step is to integrate these three control strategies into a single smart EMS, that will decide which one is the most convenient at every moment (mainly from an economic point of view, although degradation will also be considered). This smart EMS will also consider possible revenues from participating in Capacity Markets. However, the response times still need to be lowered before considering participating in the FR and Ancillary Services markets. This implies both hardware and software improvements.

Finally, an AI-based electricity market predictor will be integrated into the smart EMS. This way, the electricity prices will be estimated for longer periods than one day, potentially improving the battery management.

REFERENCES

- [1] IEA, "World Energy Outlook 2023," 2023. [Online]. Available: www.iea.org/terms
- [2] IRENA, "Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2022", 2023. [Online]. Available: www.irena.org
- [3] Red Eléctrica, "Incidente en el Sistema Eléctrico Peninsular Español el 18 de junio de 2025". [Online]. Available: [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://d1n1o4zeyfu21r.cloudfront.net/WEB_Incidente_SistemaElectricoPeninsularEspañol_18junio2025.pdf](https://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://d1n1o4zeyfu21r.cloudfront.net/WEB_Incidente_SistemaElectricoPeninsularEspañol_18junio2025.pdf)
- [4] H. C. Hesse, M. Schimpe, D. Kucevic, and A. Jossen, "Lithium-ion battery storage for the grid - A review of stationary battery storage system design tailored for applications in modern power grids", *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 12, 2017, doi: 10.3390/en10122107.
- [5] C. A. Hill, M. C. Such, D. Chen, J. Gonzalez, and W. M. K. Grady, "Battery energy storage for enabling integration of distributed solar power generation," *IEEE Trans Smart Grid*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 850–857, 2012, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2012.2190113.
- [6] P. Ferreira Torres *et al.*, "Energy Storage as a Transmission Asset—Assessing the Multiple Uses of a Utility-Scale Battery Energy Storage System in Brazil," *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 18, no. 4, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.3390/en18040902.
- [7] M. Pinho Almeida, A. R. Arrifano Manito, G. Figueiredo Pinto Filho, and R. Zilles, "Optimization tool for operating isolated diesel-photovoltaic-battery hybrid power systems using day-ahead power forecasts," *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, vol. 15, no. 4, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1063/5.0156371.
- [8] Y. Shi, B. Xu, D. Wang, and B. Zhang, "Using Battery Storage for Peak Shaving and Frequency Regulation: Joint Optimization for Superlinear Gains," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. PP, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TPWRS.2017.2749512.
- [9] S. Tibude, G. Goyal, A. Ranjan, and S. Bodkhe, *Advanced Energy Management Strategies for Hybrid Energy Storage Systems in Electric Vehicles: A Comprehensive Review*. 2025. doi: 10.1109/ICPC2T63847.2025.10958756.
- [10] O. Schmidt, S. Melchior, A. Hawkes, and I. Staffell, "Projecting the Future Levelized Cost of Electricity Storage Technologies," *Joule*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 81–100, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.joule.2018.12.008.
- [11] AEMO, "Ancillary Services Market Report. Australian Energy Market Operator." Available: <https://www.aemo.com.au/energy-systems/electricity/national-electricity-market-nem/system-operations/ancillary-services>
- [12] "PVOP Project: Digitalization of Photovoltaic Systems. Horizon Europe Programme." Available: <https://pvop.eu/>
- [13] ENTSO-E, "Market Report 2023", Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/about/>